

Microbial Ecosystems Transversal Theme

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EMBL's Current Programme: "Molecules to Ecosystems"

How molecules and organisms form complex and dynamic ecosystems?

How molecules and organisms respond and adapt to different environments?

The Transversal Themes

EMBL will build on its core strengths in molecular biology to gain a mechanistic understanding of life in context

Transversal themes:

Microbial Ecosystems
Planetary Biology
Infection Biology
Human Ecosystems

We live in a world of microbes

Microbes are the most ancient form of life on Earth and they are constantly shaping our planet

More than a trillion (10^{12}) different microbial species exist

Microbes colonise every biotic and abiotic surface on Earth

Microbes mostly live in communities

MICROBIAL ECOSYSTEMS:
Microbial communities in their environment

The human gut microbiome - a model microbial community

The gut microbiome is the largest microbial community of the human body

Microbial community we know the most about
Key characteristics, relevant for many communities
An avalanche of new tools/technologies
Importance for human health

The human gut microbiota is a prime example to study microbial ecosystems

Aims

Understand functional diversity of microbial species and strains

Dissect the interactions and properties of microbial communities

Investigate the interplay of microbial communities and their environment

Modulate microbiomes and their interactions

From microbes to ecosystems and their modulation.

Nearly all gut microbes are *terra incognita*

- ▶ Most genes in the gut microbiome are of unknown function (**dark genetic matter**) and unclear how their group in units (complexes, pathways)
- ▶ Limited available tools & resources to tap into this vast functional diversity
- ▶ This lack of knowledge hampers our ability to understand microbiome roles, harness microbiome functions for biotech, or to modulate microbiomes

Elephant in the room in the microbiome research

All prevalent and abundant microbes look nothing than our model bacterial species

Selecting two species from different genera as proof-of-principle

Phocaeicola vulgatus

Bacteroides uniformis

- ✓ High abundance
- ✓ High prevalence
- ✓ Important Biology
- ✓ Genetically tractable
- ✓ Easy to grow and manipulate
- ✓ Strain availability
- ✓ Some tools but no available resources
- ✓ Not fully unknown

Maier et al. 2018 Nature

The Flagship Project: Establishing new model species for the human gut microbiome

Bacteroides uniformis, Phocaeicola vulgatus

ME TT flagship project- the team

Heidelberg

Bork, Huber, Savitski, Typas,
Zeller, Zimmermann,
Zimmermann-Kogadeeva

EMBL-EBI

Finn, Iqbal, Lees, Martin

Alumni labs

Maier (Tübingen), Mateus
(MIMS), Patil (MRC), Saez-
Rodriguez (HD), Selkrig (Aachen)

16 groups & growing
Quarterly meetings > 50
people

Flagship Project - complementary approaches & biology

SP1- Systematic genetic resources (lead - Typas)

SP5- from strain to species (lead - Zimmermann)

(Xeno)metabolism & drug resistant capacities

SP2- Protein Complexes (lead - Savitski)

Cross-Linking MS

Surface protein machines
(sensing, transport, biogenesis)

Crosslinker

SP3- Metabolic network (lead - Zimmermann-Kogadeeva)

SP4- Pangenome (lead - Finn)

New functional units, mobile elements, BGCs-chemistry

Select highlights

Resources & Tools

New tools for identification of bacterial biosynthetic gene clusters

Activity based proteomics to map functional complexes

Carroll *et al.* bioRxiv 2021
Mateus *et al.* Nature 2020

Databases

Unified catalogue of microbial (meta)genomes; >200K ref genomes in MAGNIFY

Dedicated web-browser for Gut microbes

Almeida *et al.* Nature Biotechnology 2021

Phage revolution

Mapping phage diversity in gut

Retrons - a new prevalent phage defense system

Camarillo-Guerrero *et al.* Cell 2021
Bobonis *et al.* Nature 2022

Engagement the wider community through collaborative projects

BlueRemediomics

Zimmermann Group and Eawag

MICRObiome Biobanking Enabler

Four group leaders from ME TT involved in the proposal

Molecular and mechanistic insights into the biotransformation of organic pollutants in wastewater treatment plants

Developing protocols for biobanking microbiomes from a range of different biomes

Engaging with scientific community

EMBL facilitates microbiome research & training

Achievements

Research Articles

Internal and external meetings

Microbial Culturing Facility

Institutional collaborations

SymbNET Twinning Project (IGC, ITQB, Lausanne, Kiel)

Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research (meeting, MoU & **postdoctoral fellowship program**)

Leverhulme Centre for the Holobiont

Engagement

Microbial dark matter- new model organisms (engaging community)

Member states visits

Teaming and Twinning proposals

Microbial automation Facility at EMBL

Automation for atmosphere-controlled microbial work at scale.

Protocols for culturomics & generation of different genetic libraries.

Ideal setup for large-scale experiments for phenotypic characterization.

Development of new protocols and automated pipelines.

Enabling users to perform their research and maximizing outreach!

Impact

EMBL provides unique resources, tools, and functional insights to study microbial ecosystems.

Establish EMBL as hub for dissemination

Hub of open resources and tools

of knowhow, tools & resources for functional research of microbial ecosystems.

Center for training and outreach

Train internal and external researchers, co-develop new pipelines, link with other facilities emerging on the field.

Novel types of services

Provide services based on established workflows in the facility (e.g., strain isolation, genetic libraries...).

EMBL

Potential ways of getting involved with us

Scientific Visitor Programme

Enabling external scientists and students to benefit from new collaborations, technologies and state-of-the-art equipment

vp@embl.org

Name of the investment	Investment 1: Promoting international cooperation and participation in Horizon Europe and EIT projects
Name of the call	ERC Visiting grants
Focus/objective of the call	The aim of the call is to support the participation of excellent researchers from Slovakia in the research teams of ERC grantees. The call will provide scholarships for a maximum of 6 months to enable participation in an ERC project, thus increasing the possibility of obtaining such a project. The recipient of the visiting grant must physically participate in the ERC grantee's team.

visiting-fellowship-programmes@ec.europa.eu

Unlocking the Gut Microbial Functional Diversity

DEC 2024

~~7-8 Dec 2020~~

EMBL Large Operon
Heidelberg | Germany

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Thank you and questions

Molecular sociology of the cell: *Mycoplasma pneumoniae* (MPN)

Visualizing translation dynamics at atomic detail inside a bacterial cell

Cryo-electron tomography & sub-tomogram analysis

Animate translation elongation with 13 ribosome conformation states inside native cells and after antibiotic treatment

Bioinformatic analysis of ribosomal protein extensions

Extensions of ribosomal proteins found in MPN are common throughout the bacterial kingdom

Statistical modelling of polysomes

Polysome formation involves a local coordination mechanism that is mediated by the ribosomal protein L9

Linking TT research to structural biology

Tinidazole, is an antiprotozoal drug
metabolized by gut bacterium *B.*

Mariia Beliaeva

thetaiotaomicron

*Knocking out BT_1148 gene
decreases sensitivity (MIC) towards
tinidazole, but nitroreductase activity
remains*

no substrate-bound structures

Structures for the eight *Bt* nitroreductases